

THE ROLE OF FIBRE-MATRIX ADHESION IN
CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC
COMPOSITES : A MICROSTRUCTURAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The role of fibre-matrix adhesion in defining the key properties in carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites is discussed with reference to two composite materials: one with optimised fibre matrix adhesion, commercial APC-2, and a control carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composite with a non optimised fibre-matrix interface. The technique of directly observing failure processes in such fibre reinforced thermoplastics by fracturing the specimens inside a scanning electron microscope is also introduced. The results show that good fibre matrix adhesion is necessary for optimum translation of the fibre properties and full utilization of the PEEK matrix toughness in carbon fibre reinforced PEEK. This criterion is achieved in APC-2.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics are a class of advanced structural composite materials of particular interest to the aerospace industry. A commercially available example of such a material is APC-2, which consists of 61% by volume of continuous, collimated high strength carbon fibres in a matrix of poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK). APC-2 demonstrates superior properties compared with traditional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites in particular, high strength, toughness, damage tolerance and environmental resistance.

The excellent properties exhibited in this system have been achieved via a process of control and optimisation of the constituent materials, the production process and the fibre-matrix interface. The level of fibre-matrix adhesion is an essential factor in determining the properties of a

composite material. Studies of more brittle composite systems such as carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resins have shown that the level of fibre-matrix adhesion can dramatically influence properties in these systems [1-4]. Good adhesion is necessary for optimum translation of fibre tensile properties whilst reduced adhesion often increases toughness through such energy absorbing mechanisms as debonding at the fibre-matrix interface and fibre pull-out. The optimum adhesion level in these brittle composites may have to be a compromise between these two extremes. In a tough composite system other factors may influence the optimisation of interfacial strength.

The purpose of this paper is to discuss the role of fibre-matrix adhesion in carbon fibre reinforced PEEK by comparing the fracture characteristics of the optimised, commercial grade of the composite (APC-2) and a control, non-optimised composite based on a fibre with nearly identical characteristics, listed in Table 1, and the identical matrix resin, to APC-2. The control composite was impregnated to give a similar fibre volume, that is, 61%, and random fibre dispersion as the optimised composite. The only difference between the two systems is in the level of interfacial adhesion between the PEEK resin and the fibre.

TABLE 1

Properties of the carbon fibres used in the APC-2 and the non-optimised control, carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites

	Fibre Diameter (μm)	Tow Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tow Tensile Strength (MPa)
APC-2	7	241	4100
Control composite	7	245	4400

(Tow tensile data obtained from fibre manufacturer)

A range of mechanical properties were determined from unidirectional laminates of each composite material to ascertain the influence of the interfacial bond strength. Direct measurement of the strength of the fibre-matrix interface in composites is not trivial. However, a useful insight may be gained into the relative strengths of the fibre-matrix interface versus the cohesive strengths of the matrix or the fibre by examining the fracture surfaces of failed specimens by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Additional information about the failure mode can be obtained if crack propagation is directly monitored as it occurs. This is possible by allowing fracture to occur inside the chamber of a scanning electron microscope using a specially designed fracture stage and a modified "mini" version of the test of interest. In this work, the double cantilever beam test for determining interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{1C} , and the transverse flexural strength test were modified, as illustrated in Figure 1, to allow "in situ" observation of the failure processes.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

APC-2 and the control carbon fibre PEEK prepreg were moulded into unidirectional laminates using the recommended method [5]. 0° tensile, 0° compression (IITRI test) and transverse flexural strength (TFS) tests were carried out using the recommended procedures [5]. Interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{1C} , was determined by the double cantilever beam

(DCB) test [6]. Small sections from the resulting DCB and TFS fracture surfaces were gold coated and examined by SEM.

A modified transverse three point bend test was carried out inside a scanning electron microscope using a Hexland straining stage [7]. A unidirectional 35 x 2 x 5mm sample was polished on one side transverse to the fibres, notched, and lightly gold coated. Some samples were etched to highlight the fibre ends and reveal the spherulitic morphology of the PEEK matrix [8]. The samples were placed, polished side up, between the jaws of a three point bend attachment on the tensile stage as illustrated in Figure 1(b). The jaws were driven in compression until a crack developed, then the load increase was halted. Still photographs were taken when the crack arrested. The sample was then reloaded and the whole process repeated. After the experiment the sample was removed and one fracture surface gold coated for subsequent SEM examination.

A modified "razor blade test" [9] was chosen for observing crack propagation in the "in situ" SEM study using a specifically designed straining stage mounted inside the scanning electron microscope [10]. A small section of composite, approximately 15 x 0.5 x 2mm was polished on a side parallel to the fibres and lightly gold coated. The composite sample was mounted polished side up on one end clamp of the stage and driven into the stationary razor blade at speeds of the order of 0.5-1mm/min with the blade parallel to the prepreg layers as illustrated in Figure 1(b). A crack is formed ahead of the blade which is observed as it progresses through the sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the laminate mechanical tests on the two composite materials are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Mechanical properties of APC-2 and the non-optimised, control, carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites

Mechanical Property		Composite	
		Control	APC-2
0° tension	Strength (MPa)	1382 (120)	2092 (73)
	Modulus (GPa)	138.3 (1.6)	146.1(0.9)
	Strain (%)	1.03 (0.10)	1.39 (0.1)
0° compression	Strength (MPa)	1060 (39)	1215 (48)
Transverse flexural strength (MPa)		53.6 (2.8)	152.5(7.4)
Interlaminar fracture toughness G_{1c} (kJ/m ²)		1.01 (0.15)	2.68 (0.57) stable 2.09 (0.38) unstable

Standard deviations in parentheses

The fibre dominated properties, 0° tension and compression, are fundamental to the design of a composite structure since they define its

stiffness and strength. The results show that fibre-matrix adhesion level does not significantly influence the tensile modulus of each composite and that both values obtained are close to those predicted by the "rule of mixtures". It is only necessary to have good contact between fibre and matrix to yield maximum stiffness in carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites. Tensile strength however is markedly dependant on interface strength. The interface is therefore playing the important role of transferring stress between fibre and matrix. Since the tensile strength of a composite relies on this ability the stronger the interface the better the stress transfer capability hence the laminate strength. The compressive strength is less sensitive to interfacial adhesion level than tensile strength because, although stress transfer ability is still important the compressive and shear moduli of the matrix which determine the ability to support the fibres in compression dominate.

The non-fibre directional properties of a unidirectional composite are expected to be directly affected by the level of fibre-matrix adhesion since it is this adhesion which essentially holds the composite together. The results of the transverse flexural strength and interlaminar fracture toughness tests on the two materials together with the respective "in situ" microscopy studies confirm this expectation. Selected scanning electron micrographs taken during and after the "in situ" transverse three point bend test are shown for the two materials in Figures 2 and 3. In the control composite the crack easily zips open the fibre-matrix interface revealing bare carbon fibres and without deforming the matrix. In APC-2, although the crack moves close to the interface and prefers to follow the contours of the fibre surfaces the failure is truly cohesive in the PEEK matrix. The transverse flexural strength is therefore limited by the matrix strength. This cohesive failure mode allows the PEEK to deform considerably resulting in a ductile layer adhering to the fibre surface. Figure 3(c) also demonstrates the effect of crack propagation rate on the appearance of the fracture surface. In the fast crack propagation region on the right hand side of 3(c) the fibres are completely covered with resin which shows a fine microductility. At the slower rate region on the left hand side the resin has time to deform further and draw away from the fibre into long ductile tufts. This observation has already been reported in interlaminar fracture toughness studies [11].

The role of fibre matrix adhesion in the interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fibre reinforced PEEK can now be explained. In the control composite a steady debonding of the fibre-matrix interface along the length of the double cantilever beam means that the interface fails before the ductility hence toughness of the PEEK matrix can be realised. The optimum composite toughness in the tough PEEK matrix system can only be obtained therefore when the fibre matrix interface is stronger than the matrix as in APC-2. Comparative micrographs of the razor blade test for the two materials are shown in Figure 4 where the influence of the interface strength on the failure processes can be clearly observed.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study show that good fibre-matrix adhesion, such that the strength of the fibre-matrix interface is greater than the cohesive strengths of either the matrix or the fibre, is essential for optimum strength, stiffness and toughness of carbon fibre reinforced PEEK

composites. The fibre matrix interface in commercial APC-2 achieves this criterion.

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REFERENCES

1. Curtis, P.T. and Morton, J., International Conference of Composite Materials IV, 1984, p219.
2. Drzal, L.T., Rich, M.J. and Lyoyd, P.F., Adhesion of Graphite Fibres to Epoxy Matrices: I. The Role of Fibre Surface Treatment. J.Adhesion, 1982, 16,1.
3. Robinson, R., Lehmann, S., Askew, G., Wilford, D., Megerdigian, C., and Papalia, R., 7th International SAMPE Conference, Munich, 1986.
4. Norita, T., Matusi, J., and Matsuda, H.S., Composite Interfaces ed H Ishida and J Koenig, Elsevier Science Publishing Co, 1986, pp123-132.
5. Aromatic Polymer Composites Data Sheets, Imperial Chemical Industries PLC, 1986.
6. Leach, D.C., Curtis, D.C, and Tamblin, D.R., The Delamination Behaviour of Carbon Fibre/PEEK Composites, ASTM Symposium on Toughened Composites, Houston, March 1985, to appear in ASTM Special Publication.
7. Hexland Electron Microscopy Technology Data Sheet No. EMT049.
8. Peacock, J.A., Fife, B., Nield, E., and Crick, R.A., Examination of the Morphology of APC-2 Using an Etching Technique, Composite Interfaces ed. H Ishida and J Koenig, Elsevier Science Publishing Co, 1986, pp229-304.
9. Barlow, C.Y., and Windle, A., Razor Blade Test for Composite Toughness, J. Mat. Sci. Letters, 1985, 4, 233.
10. Brown, D.J., Windle, A.H., Gilbert, D.G., and Beaumont, P.W.R., Dynamic Studies of Peel Failure in Metallized Polyester Films, J. Mat. Sci., 1986, 21, 314-320.
11. Crick, R.A., Leach, D.C., Meakin, P.J., and Moore, D.R., Interlaminar Fracture Morphology of Carbon Fibre/PEEK Composites, J. Mat. Sci., to be published.

Figure 1 Sample geometries used in the study

- (a) the standard DCB and TFS tests and
 (b) the modified DCB and TFS tests used in the dynamic
 "in situ" SEM experiments
 (not to scale)

a) double cantilever beam

transverse flexural strength

b) "razor blade" test

notched three point bend

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of transverse flexural failure in the non-optimised, control, carbon fibre/PEEK composite. (a) Selected micrograph taken during "in situ" SEM experiment with crack running from right to left and (b) micrograph of fracture surface taken after experiment.

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrographs of transverse flexural failure in APC-2 with etched cross section:(a), (b), selected micrographs taken during "insitu" SEM experiment with crack running from right to left (c),(d), Micrographs taken after the experiment. In (c) the crack moved rapidly from right to centre, arrested when the load was relaxed then proceeded slowly to the left as the composite was reloaded. Photo (d) shows a close up of the slow crack region.

Figure 4. Micrographs of "insitu" razor blade test:(a) overview showing razor blade driven into composite, (b),(c) close-up of crack formed ahead of blade in (b) control composite and (c) APC-2.

